

Supplementary Figure S1 Full immunoblot of CsGPX4 agroinfiltrated in *C. sinensis* (approximately: 11 kDa) and *N. benthamiana* (23.3 kDa). (Left) CsGPX4 in *N. benthamiana* in comparison of EV and negative control (Right) CsGPX4 in *C. sinensis* in comparison of EV and same negative control. M: marker

Supplementary Figure S2 Full immunoblot of AtGPX8 agroinfiltrated in *C. sinensis* (approximately: 11 kDa) and *N. benthamiana* (23.3 kDa). (Left) CsGPX4 in *N. benthamiana* in comparison of EV and negative control (Right) CsGPX4 in *C. sinensis* in comparison of EV and same negative control. M: marker; red arrow pointing at faint band.

Supplementary Table S1 Primers for stable transformation experiments

Experiment	Sequence 5'-3'
Transformation vector: pCAMBIA1380- CsGPX4	F- CACGGGGGACTCTAGATGACAAGCCAATTTATACAAAACC R- TATGGGTAGTCGACGGGAGAGGCCCAAGAGCTTC
cDNA confirmation	F: ATGACAAGCCAATTTATACA R: CCAAGAGCTTCTTGATGT
CsGPX4 primer walking	F: AAGTTGTCTAAGCGTCAATT R: GACCAGCTCGAATTTCCC
RT-qPCR	F: TGACTTATCTGTCAAGGATGCC R: AACTATGAGTAAGACTTTGCCTTTG

Supplementary Table S2 Primers for Agroinfiltration experiments

Experiment	Sequence 5'-3'
Subcellular Localization Vector: Mvenus- Csgpx4	F-TGGAGAGAACACGGGGGACTCTAGAATGACAAGCCAATTTATACAAAACCC R- GCCCTTGCTCACCATGGTACCGGAGAGGCCCAAGAGCTTC
Agroinfiltration Vector: 3x Ha Tag	F- GGCCTCTCCTACCCATACGACGTTCTG R- TGCATGCCTGCAGGTCGACTCTAGATTATAGAGAAGCGTAATCTGGAAC
Agroinfiltration Vector: CsGPX4	F- CTCTCGAGCTTTTCGCGAGCTCATGACAAGCCAATTTATACAAAACCC R- GTATGGGTAGGTACCGAGCTCGGAGAGGCCCAAGAGCTTC
Agroinfiltration Vector: AtGPX8	F- TCTCGAGCTTTTCGCGAGCTCATGGCGACGAAGGAACCAG R- TATGGGTAGGTACCGAGCTCGGAGATATTCAGAAGATTCTTTATG

Data S1 Plasmid map of sable transformation vector PCAMBIA-138N-GPX4

Data S2 Plasmid map of Agrob infiltration vector PCAMBIA-1300-35s-L279-GPX4

Data S4 Plasmid map of Agroinfiltration vector for subcellular localization Mvenus_GPX4

Data S5 Plasmid map of Agroinfiltration vector for RNA silencing suppressor

Supplementary Table S3 List of isoform proteins with statistically significant fold change labeled on volcano plot from shotgun proteomics from same homolog

Accession ID	Protein name	p Value	Log2FC
Cs_ont_9g010810.1	GSTU7	0.0375	-0.8744691
Cs_ont_9g010840.1	GSTU7	0.0212	-0.8365011
Cs_ont_1g019730.1	NMT1	0.00187	-1.7369656
Cs_ont_1g019740.1	NMT1	0.00259	-1.5849626
Cs_ont_4g019670.1	MAP65	0.01493	-0.9175378
Cs_ont_4g019670.3	MAP65	0.01493	-0.9175378
Cs_ont_4g019670.2	MAP65	0.01493	-0.9175378
Cs_ont_8g025420.1	UGT74E2	0.01937	-1.2630344
Cs_ont_2g006000.1	TIR1	0.01516	-1.5849625
Cs_ont_4g022570.8	SUS4	0.03304	-0.8155755
Cs_ont_4g022570.7	SUS4	0.03304	-0.8155755
Cs_ont_4g022570.6	SUS4	0.0363	-0.8318772
Cs_ont_4g022570.1	SUS4	0.0363	-0.8318772
Cs_ont_4g022570.2	SUS4	0.0363	-0.8318772
Cs_ont_4g022570.4	SUS4	0.0363	-0.8318772
Cs_ont_4g022570.3	SUS4	0.0363	-0.8318772
Cs_ont_4g022570.5	SUS4	0.0363	-0.8318772
Cs_ont_1g021000.2	SNRK2.4	0.01378	1
Cs_ont_1g021000.1	SNRK2.4	0.01378	0.80735492
Cs_ont_5g032610.1	SNRK2.4	0.01674	1.08746275
Cs_ont_9g001770.2	BXL2	0.03872	1.18057233
Cs_ont_9g001770.1	BXL2	0.04784	1.06711413

Supplementary Figure S3 The T-DNA insertion site was identified through whole-genome sequencing and mapped to the 5' untranslated region (5' UTR) of SWEET2 (Cs_ont_2g002980.3) on chromosome 2 (chr2:1,646,389 on the negative strand). Arrow indication of T-DNA insertion point; Red; promoter region; blue: UTR; yellow: CDS. Sequence obtained from citrus.hzau.edu.

>Cs_ont_2g002980.3; chr2:1,643,759-1,646,458 (-)

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Supplementary Figure S4 Subcellular localization of CsGPX4 in *N. benthamiana*. Confocal laser scanning microscopy showing the localization of CsGPX4 fused to the C-terminus of the EGFP mVenus reporter. Localization appears to be cytoplasmic. The construct was transiently

Supplementary Figure S5 Expression of GPX genes in *C. sinensis* under *Xanthomonas citri* subsp. *citri* (Xcc) and WT treatment. Transcript per million bases (TPM) values were quantified using Salmon. Results determine GPXs in *C. sinensis* are not statistically significant. n= 4

Supplementary Figure S6 Expression of GPX genes in *C. sinensis* under 2% NaCl stress and non NaCl treatment. TPM values were quantified using Salmon. Results determine GPXs in *C. sinensis* are not statistically significant except for CsGPX3. n= 3. RNA-seq data from Zhang et al., 2025.

